

Controller General of Patents, Designs and Trademarks
Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion
Ministry of Commerce and Industry

Design Application Details

Application Number: 320692-001
Cbr Number: 15490
Cbr Date: 14-08-2019 16:50:13
Applicant Name:
1. Christo Ananth,
2. Dr. S. Selvakani,
3. Dr. R. Latha,
4. Dr. S. Pushpa,
5. Dr. R. Kesavan,

Design Application Status

Application Status: Design Accepted and Published, Journal No is 40/2019 and Journal Date is 04/10/2019

[Back](#)

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.